

HISTORICAL ORIGIN AND LINGUOCULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PROVERBS AND SUBJECTS

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Annotation : this article talks about the development of proverbs and sayings. Also, the fact that proverbs reflect the culture of the people is analyzed on the example of proverbs.

Keywords: proverb, sayings, culture, people, comparison, genre

We often refer to proverbs and proverbs in our speech. A proverb is a genre of oral creativity, it is a short and concise, figurative and non-figurative, grammatically and logically complete wise phrase. Matal is a figurative expression that clearly and correctly defines a certain life event. Unlike proverbs, proverbs do not have generalizing meaning in the form of instructive advice. Although they have some similarities, they differ from each other in their own way.

The history of studying proverbs and sayings dates back to a long time ago. The first proverbs appeared in ancient times. "The origins of proverbs are hidden in their content. Most of the proverbs enter the field of production relations and traditions among people and become an integral part of this field. Unlike a proverb, a proverb is a generally accepted figurative expression that exists for emotional evaluation and is used according to the principle of alternative to a number of similar life events. If the proverb reinforces the speech with a separate content, a new whole conclusion, then the matal is included as a complete part in the conclusion.

Mahmud Koshgari, one of the great scientists of the 11th century, widely used proverbs of the peoples belonging to the Turkic family in his work "Devonu lug'atit turk". Therefore, the collection and study of Uzbek folk proverbs was started by Mahmud Koshgari in the 11th century. 275 proverbs are cited in his work "Devonu lug'otit turk". Scholars report that our proverbs and sayings were gathered together on the orders of Abbas Safavii from the ancient branches. Interest in proverbs and sayings from a literary point of view, their use in order to increase the artistry of the work and ensure the fluency of the artistic language has always been the focus of attention of the word artists. If you carefully study the works of Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmed Yassavi, Rabguzi, Lutfiy, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Munis, Ogahi, Abdulla Qadiri and dozens of other artists, you will find how many proverbs in their composition, sometimes exactly, sometimes not. can be seen to exist unchanged. Proverbs and sayings are one of the most active means of showing the folk culture, and today they are becoming one of the important topics of the process of linguocultural research in linguistics.

Folk proverbs and proverbs are particularly meaningful as they reflect the culture and heritage of the people who created them. They can be called an encyclopedia of life, a folk encyclopedia, a unique artistic-historical chronicle. They sharpen people's minds, make their speech clear and impressive, teach them to choose the right path in life, to solve life's puzzles and problems correctly. Also, proverbs and sayings are very ancient as the smallest examples of oral creativity that summarize the worldview, cultural, domestic life, and thought treasure of the people who created them. In the languages of all the peoples of the world, we find many proverbs about friendship, brotherhood and solidarity. In Uzbek folk proverbs, there are many proverbs that emphasize family, loyalty to the country, and honesty. From this it can be understood that the Uzbek people have been paying close attention to these ideas since ancient times and have passed them down to generations. We have learned from our forefathers the tasks of valuing one's family, being able to keep it united, and paying attention to the upbringing of children. One of the most important aspects of proverbs is their instructiveness. Proverbs always convey a lesson. But there are many reasons why any great idea cannot become a proverb. The thought expressed in proverbs and sayings must acquire a universal character and have a perfect artistic form, not a specific person. The admonitional character of proverbs makes them more lively and powerful.

If we analyze the meaning of proverbs and sayings, it is not difficult to understand the linguistic and cultural features reflected in them. For example: "Where the big cart moves, the small cart moves in the same direction" - this proverb has a great meaning, and through this proverb, our ancestors care about the future generation, to be an example to them. explained about the necessity. The proverbial "big cart" represents

parents and elders, while "small cart" represents children and the young generation. There are many proverbs with a similar meaning to this proverb. It can be concluded from this that in Uzbek culture, respect for parents and elders, as well as starting children and young people on the right path, has been going on since ancient times. If the heads of the family are hardworking, honest, and patriotic, their children will also follow their example. The family is the main part of the society, and it is the basis of the country's peace, well-being and prosperity. This proverb is still actively used in our language as a proof of its existence. If we analyze another proverb, "One life without knowledge, one thousand lives with knowledge." It can also be understood from this proverb that a person who spends his life acquiring knowledge will not die and will be talked about for years and centuries as an example, while a person without knowledge will live only the life given to him and then become a name. It can be understood that it will disappear without a target. Through this proverb, the widespread promotion of learning in our nation, its importance is conveyed in a short and succinct manner. It is no secret that our ancestors produced many scientists and thinkers through their ability, talent, and interest in learning and made them famous all over the world. It is not wrong to say that their works have been glorified to this day, literally living for a thousand years. Alisher Nawai, Ibn Sina, Beruni, Al-Bukhari, Amir Temur and Zahiriddin Babur are still alive among the people who have not lost their place in education due to their high knowledge. The truthfulness and vitality of this proverb has not lost its relevance even today.

As for articles, they are easier to analyze than proverbs. Artistic tools such as simile, comparison, irony, and pun are used in the articles. There is a closeness and a logical connection between the original meaning of a figurative expression and its figurative meaning. Because its meaning can be understood based on the meaning of the words themselves. Their meaning has not changed to something completely different. For example: "When the camel's tail hits the ground" - it means something that will never come true, and you can see the proof of this in life. We know that the camel's tail is short, and it never reaches the ground. It can be understood from this that this work is impossible, like a camel's tail does not touch the ground. It is not difficult to understand such idioms as in the meaning of finished work.

Metals appeared through ancient traditions, even through customs of the colonial period. Such expressions did not have a figurative meaning at the time of their initial creation, but later acquired a figurative meaning and a figurative meaning. The history of the creation of the phrase "Popugi zayib zabej" is as follows: during the reign of tsars, khans, and emirs, when a person was appointed to a new position, they used to attach a bird's feather brooch to his headdress depending on his position. High-ranking officials used to wear expensive swan feather brooches, and smaller officials wore smaller,

shorter ones made of ukki feathers. If the high-ranking officials were removed from their deeds and put in a lower one, the tassels on his headdress would also be made of shorter feathers. People who saw this would say to each other that the officials "have fallen". This phrase is currently used in our language in a figurative sense. Proverbs and proverbs become more and more refined over time, their meaning deepens.

We can say that proverbs and sayings that are used among our people and are used in written literature, movies, theater performances, press, radio and television are a clear example of the fact that the masterpiece of wisdom is still important. Proverbs, on the other hand, serve us as a reliable, time-tested resource in the field of pedagogy, that is, in the process of education. It is appropriate to use proverbs and sayings that encourage a broad education such as speech culture, behavior, communication etiquette, listening, silence, love for the country, child education, etc. effectively and appropriately.

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